

A potential fungus agent for natural control of cutworm *Pseudaletia unipuncta*

Ch. Chiranjeevi and G. M. Rao, Rice Research Unit, Bapatla; and S. Mohiddin, Agricultural College, Andhra Pradesh Agricultural University, Bapatla 522101, India

In 1989, *P. unipuncta* (also known as *Mythimna separata*, *Mythimna unipuncta*, *Cirphis unipuncta*, *Leucania unipuncta*, *P. separata*) occurred in abundance (3-5 larvae/hill) in mature rice in experimental fields. Heavy rains (174.5-246.5 mm) the first week of Nov inundated all the fields, and might have created a favorable climatic condition for pest multiplication.

But observations in the field showed many caterpillars died naturally (see figure). We examined the dead caterpillars and found them infected with a

fungus, tentatively identified as green muscardine by the Pathology Laboratory.

Fields were left without pest control to assess the potential of the fungus to control cutworms. During the period, prevailing temperatures were 31.3-28 °C (maximum) and 20.8-17.4 °C (minimum); relative humidity was 73-95% at 0830 h and 44-73% at 1730 h. No rain fell. All caterpillars were infected within 15 d.

Simultaneously, a laboratory experiment on potted plants assessed the potential of the fungus. Infected caterpillars were collected, ground, mixed with water at 2 caterpillars/liter, and sprayed on 10 potted plants. Control plants were sprayed with water. Healthy *P. unipuncta* caterpillars were released on the potted plants at 5 caterpillars/plant.

All caterpillars in all treated pots died within 48 h.

Infected caterpillars were sent to the Plant Health Clinic for isolation and positive identification of the pathogen. ■

Dead, pathogen-infected caterpillar on a rice plant.

Farming systems

Intercropping a green manure with direct seeded rice

S. A. Sattar and J. C. Biswas, Agronomy Division, BRRI, Joydebpur, Gazipur 1701, Bangladesh

Upland rice is inefficient in Bangladesh where the organic matter content of soil is very low and the crop is subjected to various adverse environments. Intercropping or mixed cropping of legumes with rice could increase total land productivity.

We experimented with four legume intercrops under upland conditions during aus (wet season first crop) 1989. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Rice variety BR21 was wet seeded (60% germination) 26 May at 100 kg/ha in rows 30 cm apart in 3- × 3-m plots. Legumes were sown between alternate rice rows the same day.

Radiation interception by *S. rostrata* and *S. aculeata* was measured 50 d after

Effect of intercropping with legume green manuring crops on grain yield of rice variety BR21.

emergence. Dry aboveground biomass of legumes except mungbean was measured. Sun-dried grain yields of rice and mungbean were recorded; rice yields were adjusted to 14% moisture.

Vigna radiata (cultivar Mubarik) and *Crotalaria spectabilis* can be intercropped with rice without significant rice yield loss (see figure). Slow-growing *C. spectabilis* and dwarf Mubarik offer rice little competition for space and light.

The luxuriant growth of *S. rostrata* and *S. aculeata* suppressed rice growth severely. They intercepted most of the radiation (79.62 and 83.77%, respectively) at the reproductive stage of rice. *S. aculeata* produced the highest shoot biomass (2.2 t/ha) (see table). ■

Dry shoot weight of green manure crops intercropped with rice. Bangladesh, 1989.

Crop	Yield (t/ha)
<i>Vigna radiata</i> (cultivar Mubarik)	0.4 ^b d
<i>Crotalaria spectabilis</i>	1.4 c
<i>Sesbania aculeata</i>	2.2 a
<i>Sesbania rostrata</i>	2.0 b
CV (%)	5.0

^a Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 1% level by DMRT. ^b Grain yield.